

MECHANICAL AND MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURAL POWER COMPOSITES

E.S.Greenhalgh^{1*}, J.Ankersen¹, L.E.Asp⁵, A.Bismarck¹, Q.P.V.Fontana², M.Houlle³, G.Kalinka⁴, A.Kucernak¹, M.Mistry¹, S.Nguyen¹, H.Qian¹, M.S.P.Shaffer¹, N.Shirshova¹, J.H.G.Steinke¹ and M.Wienrich⁴

¹Imperial College London, London, SW7 2AZ, UK

²Cytec Industrial Materials, Heanor Gate Industrial Estate, Heanor, DE75 7SP, UK

³NANOCYL S.A., Rue de l'Essor 4, 5060 Sambreville, Belgium

⁴BAM 5.3, Federal Institute for Materials Research & Testing, D-12205 Berlin, Germany

⁵Swerea SICOMP AB, P.O. Box 104, SE-431 22 Mölndal, Sweden

* Corresponding author (e.greenhalgh@imperial.ac.uk)

In memoriam of Dr. Joachim H.G. Steinke

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

Electrolyte: Bicontinuous multifunctional polymer

Fig. 1 Architecture of the structural supercapacitors and example of a working device.

Although the inherent anisotropy of polymer composites has presented daunting technical

challenges, these materials now offer engineers considerable opportunities for efficient structural design. More recently, the advent of multifunctional composites which can fulfill more than one role within a system has attracted considerable interest, providing designers with exciting opportunities to innovate [1]. Of particular interest here are structural power composites, which simultaneously carry mechanical load whilst storing/delivering electrical energy. Although the development of these composites is highly challenging, often with conflicting constituent requirements, the STORAGE consortium [2] has had considerable success in the development of these materials for automotive applications.

The focus of this paper is structural supercapacitors, the basic architecture of a single cell of which is shown in Fig. 1. This entails two carbon fibre woven lamina (electrodes) which sandwich a glass fibre woven lamina (separator), all of which is embedded within a multifunctional matrix (electrolyte). This architecture has been the focus of the research to date, leading to components such as that shown in Fig.1 having been fabricated. This paper reports on the mechanical properties and microstructures of the different reinforcement and matrix combinations for structural supercapacitors.

1.2 The STORAGE Project

STORAGE (Composite Structural Power Storage for Hybrid Vehicles) is an EU Framework 7 research programme to develop structural power materials. The particular focus has been both structural supercapacitors and structural batteries. Within the consortium, laboratory scale developments have

been undertaken by Imperial College London (supercapacitors) and Swerea SICOMP (batteries), as well as organisations such as Chalmers (electrolyte development and characterization), INASCO (cure monitoring), ETC (battery characterization) and BAM (mechanical characterization). Nanocyl have provided the CNT reinforcement whilst Cytec have scaled up the laboratory scale developments to produce a prepreg of this structural supercapacitor material. Finally, the end user has been Volvo Car Corporation, who have been pulling the technology through to application in automotive components.

The project commenced in January 2010 and finished in June 2013. The initial focus had been the development of reinforcements and multifunctional matrices. These had been brought together to produce the set of Devices listed in Table 1. These were chosen to characterize the influence of different reinforcements and matrix developments on the electrical and mechanical performance of the resulting multifunctional composite.

Table 1 Device configurations (multifunctional composites are shown in grey).

#	Type	Electrode	Matrix
A	Structural Baseline	T300 fabric	MTM57
B	Multifunctional Baseline	T300 fabric	MTM57:IL Li [2.3mol/l]
C	CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc1)	T300 CNT	MTM57:IL Li [2.3mol/l]
D	CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc2)	T300 CNT	MTM57:IL Li [4.6mol/l]
E	CNT Sized Multifunctional (conc1)	T300 AquaCyl	MTM57:IL Li [2.3mol/l]
F	CNT Grafted Structural	T300 CNT	MTM57

During prepreg production and laminate fabrication, considerable processing hurdles were encountered, and now overcome, including eliminating short-circuiting of the electrodes during autoclaving, and tailoring the cure kinetics of the multifunctional matrix. Subsequently, there has been extensive electrical and mechanical characterization of the laminates.

It has been recognised that adoption of structural power materials would be a considerable step change in design philosophy, and therefore efforts

have been made to formulate an engineering methodology for using these novel materials. The ambition is that when these materials reach levels of performance which offer real weight or volume savings, there will be a methodology in place to use them. Consequently, research has been undertaken in developing methods for optimisation of the balance between electrical and mechanical properties for a particular application. The effects of finishing processes, such as trimming and drilling, have been investigated; initial concerns had been that such processes would lead to short circuiting between the electrodes, but as long as the components are cut dry, then such problems are minimal. The effect of curvature and forming has been investigated (see Fig. 1) and demonstrated that there is no loss in performance. Finally, methods of electrically connecting the laminates have been investigated, culminating in the successful use of lightning strike protection meshes (as used on conventional aerospace structures). These engineering issues have been discussed in an associated paper at this conference [3].

Finally, the technology has been demonstrated at various levels. This includes small scale demonstration, such as replacing the roof of a radio-controlled car with a structural supercapacitor, such that the headlights can be powered. A larger scale demonstrator has been assembled; this is the bootlid of a Volvo S80 in which four stacks (each assembled from three structural supercapacitors) are embedded between composite skins. This demonstrator has been attached to Volvo's prototype car to power the boot light, and was presented at the final STORAGE meeting in Gothenburg in June 2013.

Although much of the research effort in structural power has focused on enhancing electrical properties, a critical aspect is ensuring they have competitive mechanical properties. Although the reinforcement constituents are not degraded by the modifications made to enhance electrical performance, the matrix is inherently softened by the imbuing of ionic conductivity. Therefore the aim of the work described here was to characterize critical mechanical properties of these multifunctional materials, and understand the relationships between these properties and the microstructure and fracture processes in these materials.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and fabrication

As detailed in Table 1, several structural supercapacitor configurations were investigated in which the reinforcement and matrix phases were varied. For the multifunctional materials, T300 3k carbon fibre fabrics (twill weave) and glass fibre fabrics (plain weave) were used as the electrode and separator reinforcements, respectively. Although the baseline fabric was as-received, two carbon nanotube (CNT) reinforced configurations, as developed by Nanocyl, were also investigated; *T300 CNT* had CNTs grafted onto the fibre surface whilst *T300 AquaCyl* had a CNT sizing. Regarding the matrix, the baseline was Cytec MTM57, which is a prepreg epoxy system. To imbue this with ionic conductivity, this epoxy was blended with an equal weight fraction of ionic liquid and either of two concentrations of lithium salt; conc1 (2.3 mol/l) and conc2 (4.6 mol/l). The resulting laminates were made via a prepregging route. These Devices were compared against a monofunctional structural baseline (T300/Cytec MTM57) which is referred to as Device A in Table 1. In addition, to characterize the effect of CNT reinforcement on the mechanical properties, Device F was fabricated using CNT grafted fibres with the structural matrix (MTM57).

2.2 Characterisation

Since imbuing electrical characteristics onto the matrix had been seen to reduce its mechanical properties [4], characterisation focused on matrix and fibre/matrix dominated properties of the resulting composites. Therefore, the tests presented in Table 2 were chosen for this investigation. Firstly, in-plane shear modulus and strength of the supercapacitors was characterised using the $\pm 45^\circ$ tension test whilst the compression properties were characterised using laminates containing just the electrode material. At least five specimens were tested per condition. In addition, the volume fraction of the fibres was measured using Procedure B from the ASTM standard D3171 [5].

Table 2 Mechanical test methods and stacking sequences.

Property (Test)	Standard	Stacking Sequence
In-plane shear modulus & strength ($\pm 45^\circ$ tensile)	ASTM D3039M	$[\pm CF/\pm GF]_s$
Compressive strength & modulus	DIN EN ISO 14126	$[CF_4]_s$

Following mechanical testing, the microstructure and the fracture morphology of the composites were characterized using a Hitachi S3700N-II scanning electron microscope. Prior to examination, these specimens were sputter coated with gold. It should be noted that the ionic liquid had not been removed, which reduced the resolution of the subsequent electron micrographs. However, it was felt that any attempt to remove the ionic liquid may have led to artifacts being introduced onto the fracture surfaces. Finally, polished sections were also taken of undamaged $[CF_4]_s$ laminates to characterize the microstructure. These were examined using an optical (Zeiss Axio Imager M2m) microscope.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructures

Typical polished sections of the pristine $[CF_4]_s$ laminates are shown in Fig 2. It should be noted that difficulties were encountered in polishing the multifunctional systems (Devices B to E) because of the porous and soft nature of the matrix.

Fig. 2 Polished Sections of the Six Different Devices.

First consider the structural baseline (Device A) which is shown in Fig. 2a. This material had a microstructure typical of that of a good quality woven CFRP laminate, with a uniform interply spacing, good fibre/matrix interface and negligible voidage or fibre misalignment. Next consider the baseline multifunctional configuration (Device B) which exhibited a high degree of heterogeneity in the matrix microstructure (Fig. 2b). Within and close to the fibre tows the matrix exhibited a lot of polishing damage, which was perhaps associated with a dominance of ionic liquid in these regions. However, away from the tows (i.e. in the interstitial sites between the tows), large ‘islands’ of structural epoxy were apparent. These consisted of sites typically of the order of 500 microns in size, containing a skin/core structure (i.e the outer layers surface was smooth whilst the interior contained small isolated pores). Finally, in some sites evidence of voidage at the interlaminar interfaces was apparent.

Next (Fig. 2c) consider the influence of CNT grafting on the fibres in the multifunctional composite (Device C). The consolidation and degree of voidage of this laminate appeared to have been superior to that of Device B, and there was less polishing damage (suggesting that the matrix may have been stiffer or more robust). But yet again there was heterogeneity of the matrix, with the epoxy phase dominating at the interstitial sites. Doubling the concentration of the lithium salt in this configuration led to a subtle change in the morphology (Fig. 2d). There appeared to have been larger pores in the epoxy dominated regions, although the heterogeneity of the matrix was similar to that of the Devices B and C. Changing from grafted to CNT sizing (Device E) led to reduced voidage and a better composite microstructure (Fig. 2e). Again islands of epoxy rich matrix were evident in the interstitial sites, but there was less polishing damage to the fibre tows, suggesting a stiffer matrix. Finally, the structural epoxy with CNT grafted carbon fibres (Device F) had a microstructure almost identical to that of the structural baseline (Device A) with negligible voidage (Fig 2f).

3.2 In-Plane Shear Results

The in-plane shear strength and moduli are tabulated in Table 3 and illustrated in Fig. 3. Device A had a strength and stiffness typical of a woven CFRP laminate with a structural epoxy [6]. Similarly, the structural epoxy with CNT grafted fibres (Device F) had a reasonable in-plane shear

performance, although inferior to that of the structural baseline. Both these Devices failed via translaminar fracture of the fibres following necking (and some scissoring of the plies), as is typical for this test condition [8]. However, the introduction of the ionic liquid (Device B) led to a greatly reduced in-plane shear stiffness and strength; of the order of 10% of the performance of the structural baseline. The presence of the CNTs (particularly for Devices C and E) recovered some of the performance, with these materials having about 25% and 22% of the shear stiffness and strength respectively of the structural baseline (Device A).

Table 3 In-plane shear performance of the six different devices.

Device	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Shear strength (MPa)
Device A Structural Baseline	3.52 ±0.16	106.04 ±3.66
Device B Multifunctional Baseline	0.41 ±0.21	9.21 ±1.18
Device C CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc1)	1.04 ±0.08	25.48 ±3.44
Device D CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc2)	0.45 ±0.05	14.09 ±0.48
Device E CNT Sized Multifunctional (conc1)	0.85 ±0.18	22.48 ±3.51
Device F CNT Grafted Structural	3.11 ±0.13	80.13 ±1.56

Fig. 3 In-plane shear performance of the six Devices.

3.3 Compression Results

Table 4 Compression performance of the six Devices.

Device	Compression Strength X_c (MPa)	Young's Modulus E (GPa)
Device A Structural Baseline	619.1 ±36.8	53.6 ±3.83
Device B Multifunctional Baseline	292.3 ±33.4	58.5 ±4.71
Device C CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc1)	294.9 ±9.5	52.0 ±4.83
Device D CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc2)	153.2 ±14.4	46.9 ±5.61
Device E CNT Sized Multifunctional (conc1)	170.2 ±7.2	47.5 ±4.96
Device F CNT Grafted Structural	506.6 ±37.1	60.6 ±5.23

Table 5 Fibre volume fraction and normalized compression moduli of the six Devices.

Device	v_f	$\frac{E}{v_f^{55\%}}$ (GPa)
Device A Structural Baseline	45	65.0 ±4.65
Device B Multifunctional Baseline	51	63.4 ±5.10
Device C CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc1)	44	65.0 ±6.05
Device D CNT Grafted Multifunctional (conc2)	42	61.2 ±7.33
Device E CNT Sized Multifunctional (conc1)	49	53.2 ±5.55
Device F CNT Grafted Structural	59	56.9 ±4.91

The compression strength and moduli are tabulated in Table 4 and illustrated in Fig. 4. Because there was a variation in the fibre volume fraction between the laminates, the moduli were normalized to a fibre volume fraction of 55%, and these are shown in Table 5 and Fig. 4. Finally, typical fracture modes for the six different devices are shown in Fig 5.

Device A had a strength and stiffness typical of a woven CFRP laminate with a structural epoxy [7].

Furthermore, this exhibited (Fig 5a) a fairly localized compression failure, which was characteristic of limited delamination formation during failure [8]. Similarly, the structural epoxy with CNT grafted fibres (Device F) had a slightly inferior compressive strength (82%) to that of the structural baseline. As can be seen in Fig 5, this Device exhibited an increased propensity to delamination compared to that of the structural baseline.

Fig. 4 Compressive modulus, strength and normalized compressive modulus ($v_f=55\%$) for the six Devices.

As can be seen in Table 5 and Fig 4., an encouraging observation was that once the effect of fibre volume fraction had been accounted for, the normalized modulus of the composites were relatively insensitive to the matrix. This would suggest that under relatively modest loading the softer matrix would not disadvantage the mechanical performance of the material. This bodes well for using these materials in structural applications.

Considering the influence of multifunctional matrix on the compression strength (Table 4), as had been seen with the in-plane shear results, there was a large drop in performance. The multifunctional baseline (Device B) exhibited over a 50% reduction

in strength as compared to the structural baseline (Device A). This was attributed to the heterogeneity of the matrix, which was dominated by the ionic liquid phase adjacent to the fibres. This would have led to reduced fibre support, and promotion of fibre/matrix debonding. Device B (Fig. 5) had a localized translaminar failure, which was consistent with negligible delamination during failure [8].

It was evident that introduction of grafted CNTs to this multifunctional matrix (Device C), had not recovered the compressive performance. Furthermore, increasing the lithium salt concentration (Device D) or using CNT sized fibres (Device E), led to even further reductions in compressive strength; 25% of that of the structural baseline (Device A). It was apparent that these three devices had exhibited significant delamination prior to compressive failure, since the failure mode was ‘green stick’ [8]. This suggests that these configurations were susceptible to delamination.

Fig. 5 Compressive Failure modes for Device A (structural baseline), Device B (multifunctional baseline), Device C (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc1), Device D (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc2), Device E (CNT Sized Multifunctional conc1) and Device F (CNT Grafted Structural). 2mm laminate thickness.

4 Fractographic Observations

Following mechanical testing of the $\pm 45^\circ$ in-plane shear specimens all but the structural baseline (Device A) were found to have delaminated at the glass fibre/carbon fibre ply interface. These surfaces was subsequently exposed to allow characterization of the matrix morphology, and relate it to that observed in the bulk matrix studies [9].

Overall, in all multifunctional devices examined there was a high degree of heterogeneity in the

matrix morphology. In particular, the ionic liquid constituent tended to be dominant close to the fibres, whilst in the interstitial sites (i.e. tow cross-over points), the structural epoxy dominated. The following observations were based on general trends between the different device configurations.

Fig. 6 Morphology of the glass-fibre delamination surface in Device B (Baseline multifunctional), Device C (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc1), Device D (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc2) and Device E (CNT Sized Multifunctional conc1).

4.1 Baseline Multifunctional (Device B)

Fig. 7 Morphology of the glass-fibre delamination surface in Device B (Baseline multifunctional), Device C (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc1), Device D (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc2) and Device E (CNT Sized Multifunctional conc1) x1000

The delamination morphology at the glass fibre surface in Devices B to E are shown in Figure 6. Unfortunately, it was apparent that the multifunctional baseline (Device B) had a high degree of voidage at the ply interface, leading to a smooth exposed surface. However, the sites which did exhibit bonding had a porous structure, as

illustrated in Figure 7. It should be noted that these pores are not voids, but would have contained ionic liquid. The pores varied in size, from 1 to 10 microns, and did not appear to be interconnected.

Fig. 8 Detail of the matrix morphology in Device B (Baseline Multifunctional)

Fig. 9 Sheathing of the matrix over the fibres in Device B (Baseline Multifunctional)

Further detail of this microstructure, and the morphology close to the fibre/matrix interface is shown in Figure 8. The detail of the bonding between the fibres and matrix can be seen, which illustrates that bonding was fairly heterogeneous, with large regions with no mechanical bond (but good ionic conductivity). However, in some regions sheathing of the fibres by the structural component of the matrix was identified (Fig. 9). Here it was apparent that there was no direct contact between the glass fibres and the ionic liquid (i.e. pores). Such a morphology would be insulate the active electrode (fibres) from the electrolyte if it had developed at the carbon fibres, but perhaps would be preferential at the glass fibre separator (as in Fig 9.)

4.3 Influence of CNTs (Devices C, D and E)

Fig. 10 Pockets of structural matrix beads in Device C (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc1)

As can be seen in Fig 6, the addition of CNTs to the fibres (Devices C, D and E) appeared to have led to enhanced wetting of the matrix to the fibres during fabrication, since the degree of voidage was

considerably less than that of the baseline multifunctional (Device B).

Firstly consider the carbon fibres with grafted CNTs, with a lithium salt concentration of 2.3 mol/l (Device C). The morphology of the matrix was akin to that of Device B, with a porous structure throughout the matrix. However, in some sites (Fig. 10), beads of structural matrix were apparent. These were sites at which there had been a higher concentration of the ionic liquid, leading to the structural epoxy having formed isolated beads of material. Clearly such sites would have poor structural performance, but superior ionic conductivity. Finally, the bonding between the carbon fibres and the matrix was akin to that of the baseline multifunctional, with pores adjacent to the carbon fibres which would facilitate good ionic access.

Fig. 11 'Island and sea' morphology of the matrix in Device D (CNT Grafted Multifunctional conc2)

Next consider the influence of increasing the concentration of the lithium salt to 4.6 mol/l on the composite morphology. The consolidation of the

composite was good, as can be seen in Fig 6. However, the matrix morphology differed from that of the lower lithium salt concentration, as can be seen in Fig 7, and in detail in Fig 11. In this instance, the matrix was much more heterogeneous, with large 'islands' (upto 200 microns in size) containing agglomerations of the bead-like structures. These islands are within a 'sea' of structural polymer with very fine pores (order of 1 micron in size). Similarly, the wetting of the carbon fibres by the matrix was more heterogeneous, with large regions dominated by ionic liquid, whilst other areas in which structural epoxy/fibre bonding was present.

Fig. 12 Localised Device E (CNT Sized Multifunctional conc1) x1000

Finally, the influence of CNT sizing rather than CNT grafting was characterized by examination of Device E. This showed relatively good bonding between the glass and carbon fibre layers although there were still regions of large voids (see Fig 6.). However, as shown in Fig 12., there were subtle differences in the microstructure. In particular, in some regions close to the fibres the structural matrix had formed an almost skeletal microstructure, with

large pores next to the fibres. Interestingly, away from these sites the structural phase was more dominant, with only small, localized pores present.

5 Concluding remarks

Fig. 13 Multifunctionality of the six different Devices; (a) normalized compression modulus versus specific capacitance; (b) compression strength versus specific capacitance; (c) shear modulus versus specific capacitance. Colour refers to carbon fibre (*black - as received; red - CNT grafted; green - CNT sized*) and shape refers to matrix (*circle - MTM57; square - multifunctional conc1; triangle - multifunctional conc2*).

The aim of this work was to characterize critical mechanical properties of these multifunctional materials, and understand the relationships between these properties and the microstructure and fracture processes in these materials. However, critical to evaluating the mechanical performance is the balance with the electrical properties. Due to the dual mechanical and electrical requirements, this balance consequently leads to conflicting microstructures; rigid and solid structures for mechanical performance, whilst porous and non-tortuous structures for ionic conductivity.

Fig 13 shows the multifunctionality of these systems by plotting the specific capacitance [10] against different structural parameters, with the pure structural configuration (Device A) also shown. Unfortunately there is no equivalent pure electrical configuration (i.e. a pure ionic liquid matrix) because such a device would not have the integrity to be electrically tested. In Fig 13, the ‘perfect’ multifunctional system would sit in the top right corner.

Firstly consider the stiffness response of these multifunctional materials; stiffness would probably be the most important factor for engineering design. The multifunctionality for compressive and in-plane shear stiffness are shown in Fig 13a and Fig 13b respectively. Regarding the former, stiffness was relatively insensitive to electrical performance, as would be expected since this is a fibre dominated property [8]. Such an observation will mean a system could be optimized for electrical performance without compromising on mechanical performance. However, for the in-plane shear performance (Fig 13b), there is a rapid decline in mechanical performance with increased electrical performance. This behavior is attributed to the more compliant the matrix, the better the access for ion transport. Clearly future research would need to identify a means to address this conflict.

Finally, regarding multifunctional design for compressive strength (Fig 13c), all the multifunctional systems exhibited inferior strength to the pure structural configurations (Devices A and F). However, the highest electrical performance (Device B) was achieved without a drop in the mechanical performance.

In summary, the research reported in this paper provides an insight into the influence of the different constituents (reinforcements and multifunctional matrices) on the composite mechanical properties,

microstructures and fracture processes. Both the reinforcement type and the matrix formulation have a strong influence on the microstructure. Consequently, it was illustrated how the microstructure influenced the resulting mechanical properties. This insight will direct future refinement and optimisation of these materials.

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